

Comparative analysis of design methods efficiency in Russian and foreign turbine cooling systems of multi-mode turbojet engines

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Abstract

The researching results turbine cooling systems designs of foreign and Russian aircraft bypass turbojet engines with an afterburner are presented. For the computational research and comparative analysis, the samples of Russian and foreign advanced by-pass turbojet engines with an afterburner with the most optimal technical characteristics were selected, their cooling systems gas-dynamic parameters were calculated at 4 critical engine operating modes. The hydraulic calculations results of various schemes for supplying cooling air to the nozzle and rotor blades of a high-pressure turbine are presented. Based on the calculation results, a comparative analysis of design methods efficiency of foreign and Russian cooling systems. The efficiency was evaluated according to the variety parameters: the amount of cooling air intake at the maximum speed and cruise mode, the amount of cooling air leakage through the axial clearances into the flow path, the amount change of cooling air intake as the flow rate through the high-pressure compressor percentage when switching from the maximum mode to cruising (adaptability of the cooling system), the cooling air temperature at the supply to the nozzle blade or rotor blade cooling cavities.

Keywords: turbine cooling system, leakage through the axial clearances, brush seal

Short biography

I was born in Transnistria. Graduated from the Moscow Aviation Institute. I specialize in aircraft engines and power plants. Now I am a graduate student at the Moscow Aviation Institute and an engineer at the Experimental Design Office named after A. Lyulka.

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